

BLACK ENGLISHSupervisor: **Bazarbayeva A.M.**Student: **Khazratkulova F.T.**

Annotation: This writing is about English vocabulary variability, and Black English. Black English, also referred to as African American Vernacular English (AAVE) or Ebonics, is a dialect of English spoken by many African Americans in the United States. Although there is controversy over its origins and legitimacy as a dialect, extensive research has revealed that AAVE has its own unique set of grammatical and phonological features that distinguish it from Standard English. While some linguists view it as a legitimate dialect, others argue that it is simply a form of slang or "broken" English. Despite ongoing debates, the study of AAVE has provided valuable insight into the complex relationship between language, culture, and identity in the United States. It has been the subject of social and political debates, particularly in the context of education, where the recognition of AAVE as a legitimate dialect has been questioned. Nonetheless, the research on AAVE has revealed that it has a consistent set of grammatical rules and structures, which demonstrate its validity as a dialect of English.

Key words: Vocabulary variability, regional dialects, sociolects, historical changes, loanwords, neologisms, Ebonics, Black English.

Vocabulary variability refers to the ways in which words can vary in terms of their form, meaning, and use. In English, there are a number of factors that contribute to vocabulary variability. Some of the key factors include regional dialects, sociolects, historical changes, loanwords, and neologisms. One of the most well-known examples of vocabulary variability in English is the differences between British English and American English. While the two varieties are largely similar in terms of grammar and

syntax, there are many differences in terms of vocabulary. For example, in British English, people might say "lorry" instead of "truck", "flat" instead of "apartment", and "queue" instead of "line".

Another important factor contributing to vocabulary variability in English is sociolects. Sociolects are the language varieties that are associated with particular social groups. For example, teenagers might have their own unique slang and vocabulary, as might people who work in certain professions. The language used by politicians and lawyers might be quite different from the language used by construction workers or artists.

Historical changes also play a role in vocabulary variability in English. Over time, the meanings of words can shift, and new words can be coined to describe new concepts or technologies. For example, the word "computer" did not exist in English until the 17th century, while the word "automobile" was not used until the late 19th century.

Loanwords are another important source of vocabulary variability in English. Loanwords are words that are borrowed from other languages. For example, many English words are derived from Latin and Greek, such as "television" and "psychology". In addition, many English words have been borrowed from other languages, such as "kangaroo" from Australian Aboriginal languages and "yoga" from Sanskrit.

Finally, neologisms are another important source of vocabulary variability in English. Neologisms are newly created words or phrases that are not yet widely used or accepted. Neologisms can arise for a variety of reasons, such as to describe new technologies or social phenomena. For example, the word "selfie" was coined in the early 21st century to describe a self-portrait photograph taken with a smartphone.

English vocabulary variability is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon that is influenced by a range of factors, including regional dialects, sociolects, historical changes, loanwords, and neologisms.

One could argue that the controversy surrounding AAVE stems from deeply ingrained societal biases and prejudices towards African American culture and language. Some linguists may be hesitant to acknowledge AAVE as a legitimate dialect because it deviates from the norms and standards of white, middle-class English. This attitude perpetuates the false belief that there is only one "correct" way to speak English, and any variation from that norm is seen as inferior.

However, linguistic research has shown that AAVE is a systematic and rule-governed dialect, with its own unique grammatical structures and phonological features. It has also been found to have roots in both West African and English dialects, reflecting the complex history of African Americans in the United States.

Moreover, AAVE has a significant role in African American culture and identity, and its recognition as a legitimate dialect can have important social and political implications. Recognizing and valuing AAVE in educational settings, for instance, can lead to a more inclusive and equitable learning environment for African American students.

In conclusion, while controversy may surround AAVE, linguistic research supports its legitimacy as a distinct dialect of English with its own grammatical rules and structures. Understanding and valuing AAVE can have important implications for promoting inclusivity and understanding in society.

The use of the term Ebonics is unnecessary and potentially harmful. While it may have been created as a way to reclaim and celebrate the unique language of African Americans, it ultimately reinforces the idea that their speech is separate and inferior to standard English. Furthermore, the controversy surrounding the Oakland School Board's recognition of Ebonics as a primary language only served to further stigmatize African American students and perpetuate the notion that they are inherently linguistically deficient.

Instead of using a term like Ebonics, which has limited acceptance among linguists and the general public, we should focus on acknowledging the legitimacy and

richness of African American English. By using alternative terms like African American Vernacular English or Black English, we can emphasize the cultural and historical roots of this unique dialect while avoiding the negative connotations associated with Ebonics.

Furthermore, we should prioritize teaching African American students standard or academic English without denigrating or dismissing their home language. Rather than treating African American English as a deficiency to be corrected, we should recognize it as a valuable and valid form of communication that deserves respect and recognition.

The use of terms like "black" and "Ebonics" to describe these linguistic features is unnecessarily divisive and may perpetuate harmful stereotypes. While it is true that certain linguistic features are more common in African American English, they are by no means exclusive to that community. Furthermore, the use of terms like "black words" may reinforce the idea that African American English is somehow separate and inferior to standard English, when in reality it is simply a different dialect with its own unique features.

Instead of focusing on these differences, we should celebrate the diversity of language and recognize that all dialects are equally valid forms of communication. Rather than labeling certain linguistic features as "black" or "Ebonics", we should simply acknowledge them as part of the rich tapestry of English dialects. Additionally, we should avoid using these linguistic differences as a way to stereotype or stigmatize certain communities, as this can be both hurtful and counterproductive.

Ultimately, the most important thing is to recognize and respect the linguistic diversity of our society, and to work towards creating a more inclusive and accepting environment for all dialects and cultures.

The emphasis on the systematic nature of Ebonics pronunciation and grammar may be overstated, and that these features are still widely regarded as non-standard or even incorrect by many speakers of standard English. While it is true that Ebonics has

its own rules and restrictions, these rules may not align with the rules of standard English and can therefore lead to confusion and miscommunication.

For example, the omission of present tense *is* and *are* in Ebonics may be perceived as a lack of proper grammar, as it deviates from the standard English rule of using present tense forms of "to be" before present participles. Similarly, the use of invariant *be* may be seen as non-standard, as it does not align with the standard English rule of using "is" or "are" to indicate present tense.

Furthermore, some critics may argue that the use of Ebonics in formal settings, such as schools or the workplace, can hinder individuals from being able to effectively communicate with those who do not understand the dialect. In these settings, it may be more advantageous for individuals to conform to the norms of standard English in order to effectively convey their ideas and connect with a wider audience.

Ultimately, while it is important to recognize the systematic nature of Ebonics pronunciation and grammar, it is also important to acknowledge the potential challenges that may arise when communicating with those who do not understand the dialect. Rather than viewing Ebonics as a separate or inferior dialect, we should work towards promoting a greater understanding and acceptance of linguistic diversity in all its forms.

While some black writers and public figures may praise Ebonics for its expressive power and cultural significance, many others view it as a hindrance to upward mobility and a marker of limited education or social status. Even some black people are critical of Ebonics, such as Maya Angelou, who used it in her poetry but found the Oakland School Board's 1996 Ebonics resolutions "threatening." Additionally, some people have criticized the teaching of Ebonics, misinterpreting it as a proposal to teach Ebonics itself or to teach in Ebonics rather than as a way to respect and incorporate it into the teaching of Standard English. While the method of contrastive analysis has been used successfully in some schools to improve Ebonics speakers' performance in Standard English, not everyone agrees that this is the best approach.

While some linguists believe that African American Vernacular English (AAVE) has its origins in English, others argue that it has roots in West African languages. These linguists point out that certain sounds, such as "th" sounds and final consonant clusters, are absent in West African languages, and that these sounds are often replaced or simplified in both AAVE and West African English varieties spoken in Nigeria and Ghana. Additionally, the tense-aspect system of AAVE, which distinguishes between completed and habitual actions, is prevalent in West African language systems. Another perspective is that AAVE shares similarities with Caribbean Creole English varieties, such as dropping "is" and "are," and permitting the dropping of word-initial "d," "b," and "g" in tense-aspect markers. These similarities suggest that some varieties of AAVE may have undergone the types of simplification and mixture associated with Creole formation in the Caribbean and elsewhere. This view proposes that American AAVE was shaped by the high proportions of Creole-speaking slaves that were imported from the Caribbean during the earliest settlement periods of the thirteen original colonies. Despite these debates, linguists agree that AAVE is a dynamic and distinctive variety of American English that is deeply tied to African American history and culture. There is also ongoing discussion regarding whether AAVE is converging or diverging from other vernacular varieties of American English. Regardless of its direction of change, AAVE will continue to be an important topic of study and discussion for years to come due to its significant role in African American literature, education, and social life. The study of AAVE has shed light on the intricate connections between language and identity and has highlighted the need for greater recognition and acceptance of linguistic diversity. Language is a dynamic and evolving entity that reflects the social and cultural contexts in which it is used. By recognizing and embracing the unique features of AAVE, we can promote greater inclusion and equity in society.

References:

1. Baugh, John. 2000. *Beyond Ebonics: Linguistic pride and racial prejudice*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
2. Green, Lisa. 2002. *African American English: A linguistic introduction*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
3. Labov, William. 1973. *Language in the inner city: Studies in the Black English Vernacular*. Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press.
4. Poplack, Shana, ed. 2000. *The English history of African American English*. Malden, MA, and Oxford, UK: Blackwell.
5. Rickford, John R. , and Russell J. Rickford. 2000. *Spoken Soul: The story of Black English*. New York: John Wiley.
6. Smitherman, Geneva. 2000. *Black talk: Words and phrases from the hood to the amen corner*. New York: Houghton Mifflin.
7. Wolfram, Walt, and Erik R. Thomas. 2002. *The development of African American English*. Malden, MA, and Oxford, UK: Blackwell